

Non-Asbestos Polybenzoxazine Composites: Friction and Mechanical Property

Chanchira Jubsilp¹, Sarawut Rimdusit², Wichukorn Lertwassana²

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Srinakharinwirot University Nakhonnayok 26120, Thailand, chanchirar@g.swu.ac.th

² Polymer Engineering Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering, Chulalongkorn University Bangkok 10330, Thailand, sarawut.r@chula.ac.th

Abstract

Effects of short carbon fiber contents on the tribological characteristics and mechanical properties of the polybenzoxazine composites can be summarized as follow.

- The addition of short carbon fiber in the polybenzoxazine composites increased flexural strength and modulus of the composites.
- At a various temperature in a range of 100 – 350 °C, the friction coefficient of polybenzoxazine composite reinforced with the short carbon fiber at 25 % by weight (a mass ratio of aramid pulp:short carbon fiber = 75:25) increased up to a temperature of 300 °C and was still maintained at 350 °C.

Based on the findings in this work, the obtained polybenzoxazine composite has high potential to be used for friction materials where high friction coefficient and modulus are required.

Application of Friction Materials

A brake system is one of the most important parts of a vehicle. The main function of the system is to decrease the speed of a vehicle. By stepping on the brake pedal, the brake pads compress against the rotor attached to the wheel, which then forces the vehicle to slow down due to friction.

Ref: <https://www.glenwoodauto.ca>

Performance Properties of Friction Materials

- ✓ Adequately high coefficient of friction
(0.35–0.45 for brake-materials in general)
- ✓ Low fluctuations in μ
(minimal sensitivity for pressure, speed and temp.; called as fade)
- ✓ Counter face friendliness
(moderately low wear)
- ✓ Adequate thermal conductivity
- ✓ Ease and repeatability in production
- ✓ Environment friendliness

Ref : Aranganathan N, Bijwe J., Wear 330–331: 515–523 (2015).

Results

Fig. 1 Flexural properties of poly(BA-35x) reinforced with various ratios of aramid pulp:short carbon fiber.

Fig. 2 Friction coefficient of poly(BA-35x) composite.

Fig. 3 Wear debris after tribological test (a) poly(BA-35x) reinforced with aramid pulp:short carbon fiber (75:25), (b) commercial asbestos brake pads.

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